

3-D-Printed Modified Butler Matrix Based on Gap Waveguide at W-Band for Monopulse Radar

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Abstract—This article presents the design and fabrication of low-loss, -weight, and -cost, modified Butler matrix in groove gap waveguide technology at W-band, implemented by additive manufacturing. The design, simulations, and measurements of each of the elements that conform to the modified Butler matrix are presented. The proposed modified Butler matrix is asymmetric and oriented to an easy assembly with a radial antenna in order to obtain simultaneous sum and difference patterns for a narrowband radar application. The measured individual components of the modified Butler matrix fit very well with the simulations. As for the full modified Butler matrix, measurements provide a 0.7% bandwidth below -20 dB for sum and difference ports centered at 94 GHz. The amplitude and phase imbalance are below 1.5 dB and 20° , respectively. This narrow bandwidth is due to the difference in length between input and output ports due to the asymmetry of the design. The total losses of the modified Butler matrix are below 1 dB.

Index Terms—Additive manufacturing, butler matrix, distribution network, groove gap waveguide (GGW), low cost, low loss, low profile, low weight, monopulse, point-to-point communications, radar, space debris, W-band.

I. INTRODUCTION

NEW applications of communication systems and radar at millimeter-wave frequencies are appearing in multiple areas of telecommunications. These applications demand viable solutions for deploying antenna systems where low losses, reduced cost, ease of assembly and low weight are of fundamental interest. These new applications have seen the light due to the assignment of new spectral bands in millimeter wave frequencies for communications and radar

systems, among others. In particular, the frequency bands 71–76, 81–86, and 92–95 GHz have been proposed in the W-band for high-speed point-to-point wireless communications [1]. Thanks to the reduction in wavelength, in these bands it is possible to obtain highly directional antennas in a practical size, which makes it possible to engineer systems that are very close to each other without causing interference [2]–[5]. In addition, radar systems can also benefit greatly from this increased directivity in antenna systems to enhance resolution and improve detection of smaller targets at greater distances. A clear application of these capabilities is the detection of space debris, in which great research efforts are being made [6]–[10]. The aim is to address the problem of the accumulation of debris from disused satellites and small particles with a few centimeters in diameter from old collisions between satellites traveling at thousands of kilometers per hour. The collision of some of these particles with active satellites or with space exploration stations could lead to their destruction.

Monopulse radar systems are currently being developed at 94 GHz [11]–[16]. Due to the wide range of W-band applications, specifically around 94 GHz, this article focuses on a proposal for a modified Butler matrix with 94-GHz design frequency. This modified Butler matrix can be coupled to an antenna to provide both a point-to-point communications system and a monopulse radar system [5], [12].

One of the typical problems of antennas at these frequencies is the high losses introduced by commonly used dielectric materials employed by substrates. Microstrip is a clear example of cheap technology, easy to access and simple to manufacture and design, but due to the properties of the available dielectric substrates, the efficiency of the antennas is greatly reduced by the high losses. Other substrate-based technologies tried to improve the efficiency. There are works that use low-temperature cofired ceramics (LTCC) technology to reduce losses in antennas based on microstrip distribution networks [17]. This technology is characterized by using a ceramic substrate with a very high dielectric constant and low losses, making it interesting for high frequencies.

Another widely used substrate-based technology is substrate integrated waveguide (SIW), which consists of the implementation of a waveguide in a substrate replacing the lateral walls with metallic vias. These metallized vias must be separated up to a certain distance to avoid leaks. Some W-band designs use this technology [13], [18]. However, despite their low cost and ease of manufacture, the distribution networks implemented

are often long and sometimes multilayered, resulting in high losses in the dielectric. The result is a very negative impact on the overall efficiency of the antenna, as shown by the examples [13], [18] with gains of 30 and 25 dBi, but efficiencies of 15% and 25%, respectively.

As a solution to the problems presented by designs based on dielectric substrate, the use of all-metal antenna systems based on waveguide is proposed. This maximizes efficiency because of the low losses associated with the systems, but makes the manufacturing and assembly process difficult. For complex flat networks based on rectangular waveguide, fabrication is normally done in two or more parts. Subsequent assembly must ensure very good electrical contact between the metal walls along the entire structure, something that is difficult and expensive to achieve for high frequencies due to manufacturing tolerances. Diffusion bonding is a monolithic metal device manufacturing technology that consists of stacking thin metal layers with the desired patterns. Specific pressure and temperature conditions are applied to these layers, allowing them to weld into a single metal part. In this way, it is possible to manufacture antennas with intricate feeding networks in waveguide with very good electrical contact between layers [19]–[22]. Despite its good performance and design versatility, this technology is very expensive and the resulting parts are very heavy because they are made of solid metal, especially if they are made of copper.

Recent gap waveguide technology has tried to solve these problems by providing a low-loss, easy-to-assemble transmission structure that does not require good electrical contact between parts. The contactless condition is achieved by replacing the waveguide metal walls by periodic metal pins. These pins generate a surface of high impedance above them and when covered by a metallic plate at a distance of less than a quarter of wavelength a stopband is generated. This stopband prevents the propagation of electromagnetic fields in a certain frequency band, so that the fields are confined within the gap waveguide path. Three basic structures based on waveguide gap have been proposed in the literature: ridge gap waveguide (RGW), groove gap waveguide (GGW) and microstrip RGW (MRGW) [23]. In this article, the GGW structure has been selected because it provides the lowest loss.

The GGW structure is similar to a rectangular waveguide with metal pins instead of solid metal walls, and so it propagates a quasi-TE₁₀ mode [24]. One of the biggest problems in manufacturing waveguide gap structures is the cost of manufacturing periodic pins. There are many designs based on waveguide gap manufactured on computer numerical control (CNC)-machined aluminum parts, a widely used manufacturing technology [25]–[28]. The problem with these periodic structures is that they require a lot of milling time and the price increases significantly. The problem increases when designs are made at higher frequencies, and a gap waveguide design in W-band requires thinner drills and longer manufacturing time.

An alternative to classic CNC machining is additive manufacturing. 3-D-printing is rapidly developing more precise and faster techniques and is being incorporated by multiple areas of industry and engineering. Typically, high-performance 3-D-printers use plastic resins or powder particles of plastic or

metal that harden and bind together to form the desired part. The application of additive manufacturing to this type of gap waveguide structures eliminates the cost problem of periodic pins, facilitates design and considerably reduces the price of final prototypes. Some works demonstrate that 3-D-printing provides good results in millimeter band designs [29]–[32]. Most of them are based on circular or rectangular waveguides and are manufactured in one piece. This can be a problem when evacuating resin or metal/plastic powder residue from the interior of intricate structures and makes internal metallization of plastic devices difficult. Several gap waveguide designs at Ka-band avoided these problems associated with additive manufacturing [33]–[35]. Specifically, in [33] we carried out a study of various GGW structures at Ka-band manufactured by stereolithography with subsequent metallization in copper. However, printing tolerances may affect depending on the frequency band, especially when printing small pins. 3-D-printing research applied to gap waveguide structures at W-band has not been reported yet. This article also aims to verify the behavior of this 3-D-printing technology in W-band gap waveguide designs.

This article is divided into five sections: Section II presents the desired behavior of the modified Butler matrix and a schematic with the basic components that are part of it. Section III details the design of each of the individual components of the modified Butler matrix, such as transitions to WR-10, dividers, bends, phase shifters, hybrids, crossovers and phase adjustment sections for the final design of the modified Butler matrix. Section IV presents the manufactured prototypes accompanied by a comparison between the measurement and simulation of each of them. Final considerations about design and measurements are discussed in Section V and conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. MODIFIED BUTLER MATRIX BEHAVIOR AND SCHEME

The modified Butler matrix proposed in this article consists of two inputs and four outputs, so that the configuration of relative phases between the outputs is equiphase for one input port and with a 90° sequential phase difference between consecutive outputs for the other input port. These two configurations were chosen to simultaneously generate a constant-phase symmetrical mode and a progressive-linear-phase rotary mode inside a radial line slot array (RLSA) antenna when both input ports are excited. The rotary mode inside the RLSA generates a sum (Σ) pattern with a pencil beam and the symmetrical mode produces a difference (Δ) pattern with a conical beam [5]. Previous works use Butler networks employing microstrip technology [36] at lower frequencies to excite RLSA monopulse antennas. As already explained in Section I, microstrip design is not feasible at 94 GHz, so the Butler matrix scheme has been redesigned in order to be implemented with gap waveguide. This article is focused only on the design and manufacture of the modified Butler matrix. In fact, the four outputs converge in a central circular cavity excited with four ports spaced every 90° that couple both modes to the radial antenna, but more details of the design and excitation of the monopulse RLSA antenna can be found at [5].

Fig. 1. Modified Butler matrix scheme for sum (port 1) and difference (port 2) configurations.

Fig. 2. GGW unit cell. (a) Structure. (b) Dispersion diagram.

The modified Butler matrix scheme that fits this monopulse configuration is presented in Fig. 1. The two first 3-dB 90° hybrids of the typical Butler matrix were substituted by power dividers because only two of the inputs are used. The corresponding 90° phase differences are rearranged along the scheme using 90° phase shifters. In this way, we avoid the use of loaded terminations in the two unused inputs. In [36], those loads were included in the microstrip design, but they were cheap and small compared to WR-10 loads.

As can be seen in Fig. 1 (ignoring the phase shifters which are a perturbation of the waveguide), the modified Butler matrix is about a horizontal plane, but not about a vertical plane. The path lengths between each input port and each output port are different, so it is necessary to introduce a phase adjustment in some sections to obtain the desired phases in the outputs. The design of a completely symmetrical Butler matrix in which all paths are the same length was discarded. The problem in this case is the size of the resulting Butler matrix, with the consequent increase in transmission losses and manufacturing cost. As the application is narrowband (less than 0.5 GHz) we preferred to implement the smaller design.

III. DESIGN OF THE MODIFIED BUTLER MATRIX

This section presents the design and simulation of each of the components that are part of the Butler matrix, as well as their interconnection to build the final modified Butler matrix.

A. Base GGW Structure

To begin with the modified Butler matrix design, we have selected the basic unit cell from which all components will be

Fig. 3. Simulations of (a) loss and (b) coupling between parallel gap waveguide with 1, 2, 3, and 4 rows of pins at both sides.

Fig. 4. Simulations of (a) loss and (b) phase shift depending on the roughness rms of the copper surfaces.

built. The GGW unit cell has a periodicity $p = 1.2$ mm and three rows of pins on the sides of the gap waveguide. Fig. 2(a) shows the dimensions of all the details of the structure. The separation $Wg = 3.25$ mm between the inner pins of the waveguide has been chosen to minimize the losses and dispersion introduced by the structure, taking into account that the cut-off frequency of the next propagated mode is at least 5% above the design frequency (94 GHz). In the dispersion diagram in Fig. 2(b), a TE_{10} mode propagates from 64.5 to 99 GHz in a single-mode band configuration. The number of rows of pins at the sides of the gap waveguide has been chosen according to the transmission losses and the coupling between parallel gap waveguides considering paths with 50 periodic pins in length. The results obtained in simulation with 1, 2, 3, and 4 rows of pins are represented in Fig. 3. In Fig. 3(a), it is clear that the behavior is not good when only one row is used, but it is very good in the rest of the cases. This is because, using a single row, the periodicity effect in the transverse direction is lost and the blockage of waveguide gap propagation is considerably reduced. In the level of coupling between parallel guides of Fig. 3(b), greater differences are observed. Acceptable coupling levels (below -40 dB) are achieved from three rows of pins on each side. Therefore, the base structure has been designed with three rows of periodic pins.

An important quality to consider in the design is the roughness of the copper surfaces obtained in the manufacturing process. As noted in [33], the roughness of the metallization process carried out by our supplier is around $0.3 \mu\text{m}$. Low roughness values increase the equivalent conductivity of the metal used, which in this case is copper. This reduces dissipative loss. Several simulations with different values of roughness rms (Rq) have been carried out to observe their effect on transmission losses and phase. Fig. 4 represents these values per centimeter for four different copper roughness

Fig. 9. Design details and values of the structural parameters of the 45° bend.

Fig. 10. Design details and values of the structural parameters of (a) original bend and (b) 90° phase shifter. All values are expressed in millimeters.

Fig. 11. Simulation of the S-parameters of the 90° phase shifter. (a) Magnitude. (b) Phase shift.

the horizontal axis, it is also necessary to design 45° bends. To do this, we have modified the structure of the 90° bend in Fig. 7 so that it has a mirror symmetry along the diagonal while keeping the unit cell structure of Fig. 1 along this axis of symmetry (see Fig. 9). This makes it possible to connect this element to any other, since the junction point is always the unit cell. Due to limitations in the orientation of waveguide ports in computer simulation technology (CST), we simulated two consecutive 45° bends whose S-parameters are similar to those presented in Fig. 8.

D. 90° Phase Shifter

For the 90° phase shifter design, we have modified the bend in Fig. 7 to introduce an additional phase shift of -90° . With this solution, we avoid having to add an additional phase-shifting element in the chain, which would mean an increase in length, but it is only enough to replace a normal bend by this new 90° phase-shifting bend. In order to add this extra phase shift, the total length of the fields inside has been slightly increased. In Fig. 10, the structures of both the original bend [see Fig. 10(a)] and the 90° phase shifter [see Fig. 10(b)] are shown. The results of the simulation are depicted in Fig. 11:

Fig. 12. Design details and values of the structural parameters of the power divider. All values are expressed in millimeters.

Fig. 13. Simulation of the S-parameters of the power divider. (a) Input reflection. (b) Transmission and output reflection.

Fig. 14. Design details and values of the structural parameters of the hybrid 3-dB 90°. All values are expressed in millimeters.

magnitude of the S-parameters [see Fig. 11(a)] and the introduced phase shift [see Fig. 11(b)].

E. Power Divider

The power divider has been designed in a Y-shape as its outputs must be parallel. The width of this design is smaller than for a T-divider with two right angle bends for parallel outputs. The details of the design and the S-parameters obtained after an optimization process are given in Figs. 12 and 13. We know from basic circuit theory [37] that in a three-port, reciprocal, lossless device such as this one, it is impossible to match all ports. However, since ports 2 and 3 are excited simultaneously when operating in reception, a good combined matching is obtained.

F. Hybrid Coupler 3 dB 90°

The 3-dB 90° hybrid coupler design is based on the existing design implemented in waveguide [38]. The main design parameters are width and length calculated from expressions in [39]. Considering a value of $a = 3$ in (1) and (2), where k is the wavenumber, the calculated width and length for the hybrid

Fig. 15. Simulation of the S-parameters of the hybrid 3-dB 90°. (a) Reflection and isolation, (b) transmission, and (c) phase difference at outputs.

Fig. 16. Design details and values of the structural parameters of the crossover. All values are expressed in millimeters.

coupler are $w = 5.60$ mm and $l = 5.83$ mm. The position of the pins (see Fig. 14) has been adjusted to obtain greater bandwidth. Both the reflection and isolation between parallel ports present a band greater than 5% [see Fig. 15(a)] with a coupling to the output ports crossing at the design frequency at a level of -3.1 dB [see Fig. 15(b)] due to losses in copper. The phase difference between outputs is practically constant throughout the 91–97 GHz band, varying between -89° and -90° [see Fig. 15 (c)]

$$w = \frac{\pi}{k} \sqrt{\frac{4(3a+1)(a+1)}{4a+1}} \quad (1)$$

$$l = \frac{\pi}{k} \sqrt{\frac{(3a+1)(a+1)}{3}} \quad (2)$$

G. Crossover

The design of a crossover is usually done by concatenating two 3-dB 90° hybrids [39]. This structure allows two transmission lines that follow different trajectories to cross keeping the coupling between them at a minimum level. As can be seen in Fig. 16, the crossover has been designed in a similar way to the hybrid, considering a value of $a = 7$ in (3)

Fig. 17. Simulation of the S-parameters of the crossover. (a) Reflection and isolation. (b) Transmission.

and (4). The calculated width and length are $w = 5.77$ mm and $l = 12.45$ mm. In order to improve the adaptation and minimize the coupling, the position of the pins has been slightly optimized. The simulation results are shown in Fig. 17. We added two small pins 0.2 mm high in the center of the crossover. These pins have been introduced to eliminate a resonance appearing at 92.15 GHz [see Fig. 17(b)]. A similar bandwidth to that obtained with the hybrid is observed, with an isolation better than -40 dB in the direct output and a transmission to the diagonal output around -0.1 dB due to losses in the copper

$$w = \frac{\pi}{k} \sqrt{\frac{(6a+1)(2a+3)}{8a}} \quad (3)$$

$$l = \frac{\pi}{k} \sqrt{\frac{(6a+1)(2a+3)}{12}} \quad (4)$$

H. Propagation Constant Adjustment for Tuning Phases

This section details the phase adjustment of the Butler matrix branches. This adjustment is necessary due to the difference in length of the branches of the modified Butler matrix, as already mentioned in Section II. Phase correction has been carried out by adjusting the phase constant of sections $S1$, $S2$, $S4$, and $S5$ of the modified Butler matrix in Fig. 18(a). Sections $S3$ and $S6$ have been kept fixed. The remaining components of the modified Butler matrix are indicated in Fig. 18(a) with the letters: T (WR-10 transition), D (power divider), B (bend 90°), P (90° phase shifter), C (crossover) and H (hybrid coupler). Several types of bend are shown in the design: Bs for a shorter bend and Bh for the half bend with 45° rotation. To facilitate matching line lengths, the bend B* will be substituted by a 90° phase shifter P. The adjustment of each section consists of modifying the width of the gap waveguide.

Fig. 18(b) and (c) shows the paths that differ in length. For a narrowband application such as this, the necessary adjustment for paths X and Y on the one hand and Z and W on the other must meet that the wrapped phase introduced at 94 GHz is the same. Therefore, the expressions (5) and (6) must be met

$$\text{Ph}(X) - \text{Ph}(Y) = n \cdot 360 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Ph}(W) - \text{Ph}(Z) = n \cdot 360 \quad (6)$$

Fig. 18. (a) Complete design of the modified Butler matrix, (b) detail of the X and Y paths, and (c) of the Z and W paths for phase adjustment.

being n an integer number and

$$\text{Ph}(X) = \text{Ph}(S1) + \text{Ph}(B) + \text{Ph}(Bs) + \text{Ph}(S2) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Ph}(Y) = \text{Ph}(Bs) + \text{Ph}(B^*) + \text{Ph}(C) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Ph}(Z) = \text{Ph}(C) + \text{Ph}(Bh) + \text{Ph}(S6) \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Ph}(W) = 2 \cdot \text{Ph}(B) + \text{Ph}(S3) + \text{Ph}(S4) + \text{Ph}(Bh) + \text{Ph}(S5). \quad (10)$$

The use of $n \neq 0$ results in a narrower band. Because one of the design choices was to maintain symmetry vertically but not horizontally, some paths must be longer than others. This prohibits using $n = 0$, but as the application is narrowband (less than 0.5 GHz), we accept this limitation. After unwrapping the phase of each one of the components of the analyzed paths, the final phase introduced is obtained. The initial result X - Y with B ends and W - Z is represented in Fig. 19. Keeping the widths of sections $S3$ and $S6$ fixed at a value of $Wg = 3.25$ mm, it is necessary to modify the width of sections $S1$ and $S2$ to a value of 2.79 mm and sections $S4$ and $S5$ to a value of 3.6 mm. It was observed that it is possible to minimize the width variation of sections $S1$ and $S2$ to 3 mm by replacing the B^* bends with 90° phase shifters (see curve X - Y with P in Fig. 19). The final phase difference represented in Fig. 19 with solid lines is $0^\circ (+n \cdot 360^\circ)$ at 94 GHz. The final values of width and length of the section $S1$ to $S6$ are shown in Table I for the phase correction of -81.79° between X and Y paths and 132.3° between W and Z paths.

To verify that the phases obtained in the outputs of the modified Butler matrix are as expected, we have calculated the total phase shift introduced by all components. The results obtained for input port 1 [see Fig. 20(a)] show a sequential phase difference of 90° . For port 2 in Fig. 20(b), the value of the phases at the outputs coincides. A maximum error of less

Fig. 19. Phase corrections between paths X and Y and paths W and Z .

TABLE I
WIDTH AND LENGTH OF SECTIONS $S1$ TO $S6$

Section	Width	Length	Section	Width	Length
$S1$	3.00 mm	8.40 mm	$S4$	3.6 mm	28.98 mm
$S2$	3.00 mm	14.04 mm	$S5$	3.6 mm	7.94 mm
$S3$	3.25 mm	8.40 mm	$S6$	3.25 mm	10.93 mm

Fig. 20. Phases at the output ports for (a) input port 1 and (b) input port 2 after phase adjustments. Phase differences are referenced to the phase at port 6.

than 2° has been found in the simulation and thus we validate the design for its manufacture.

IV. SIMULATIONS AND MEASUREMENTS

This section presents the results obtained both in simulation and in measurement of the manufactured prototypes. The prototypes were manufactured using stereolithography (SLA), a 3-D-printing technology based on UV curable plastic resin. The plastic pieces obtained were subsequently coated with 5–10 μm of copper. The tolerances are 50 μm in xy plane and 100 μm in Z -direction. The validation of prototypes includes the individual components of the modified Butler matrix to verify their behavior. Section IV-A presents only the prototypes of individual components, while measurements and simulations of the modified Butler matrix are shown in Section IV-B.

A. Individual Elements

All components of the modified Butler matrix are manufactured in two pieces. The piece in Fig. 21(a) contains a short straight section, a right angle bend, a 45° bend, a 90° phase shifter, and a 3-dB 90° hybrid. The prototype in Fig. 21(b) presents a long straight section, a power divider and a crossover. The difference in length between the short

Fig. 21. Pictures of the prototypes manufactured. (a) Piece with bend, 45° bend, phase shifter, short straight section, and hybrid 3-dB 90°. (b) Piece with power divider, long straight section, and crossover. Detail of the manufactured WR-10 transition. (c) Reverse view. (d) Obverse view.

Fig. 22. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the short straight section. (a) S_{21} . (b) S_{11} .

Fig. 23. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the long straight section. (a) S_{21} . (b) S_{11} .

and long straight sections is 24 mm, so it is possible to obtain an estimate of the measured losses per unit length of the gap waveguides. The images in Fig. 21(c) and (d) show a manufactured transition to WR-10 in detail.

All the measurements of the prototypes presented in this section show a high degree of similarity to the simulations. One of the critical points in the prototypes is the interface between the used GGW structure and the WR-10 flange. Figs. 22 and 23 depict the simulated and measured S-parameters of the short and long straight sections, respectively. The measured reflection coefficient is 15 dB higher than the simulation level, but still remains below -20 dB in a 20-GHz band. In relation to the transmission in Figs. 22(a) and 23(a), there are very low losses up to

Fig. 24. Estimated losses per centimeter derived from the transmission coefficient for the short and long straight sections (24 mm difference).

Fig. 25. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the right-angled bend. (a) S_{21} . (b) S_{11} .

Fig. 26. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the 45° bend. (a) S_{21} . (b) S_{11} .

100 GHz, from which the pins lose the ability to block propagation as seen in the scatter diagram in Fig. 2(b). In Fig. 22(a), some measured values are above 0 dB around 80 GHz that are produced by small alignment error during the calibration and measuring processes. In Fig. 24, taking into account the length difference of 24 mm between straight sections, we estimate losses between 0.05 and 0.1 dB/cm that fit well with the losses obtained in simulation considering a copper metallization with a roughness of 0.3 μm .

The results of the 90° bend and the 45° bend in Figs. 25 and 26 are also very satisfactory. The measured reflection is below -20 dB from 80 to 100 GHz with a transmission coefficient around -0.2 dB. The same applies to the 90° phase shifter, although in this case the matching level shown in Fig. 27(b) is slightly worse in both measurement and simulation. The phase difference between the right angle bend and the 90° phase shifter is represented in Fig. 28. The measurement of the phase difference fits very well with the simulation and with the result obtained in the design of Fig. 11. The measured phase difference at 94 GHz is 91°, with a variation of $\pm 5^\circ$ between 91 and 97 GHz.

With respect to the power divider, the comparison of simulation and measurement is shown in Fig. 29. Both the level and shape of the measured S-parameters meet the simulation

Fig. 27. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the phase shifter. (a) S_{21} . (b) S_{11} .

Fig. 28. Simulated and measured phase shift of the phase shifter.

Fig. 29. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the power divider. (a) S_{21} and S_{31} . (b) S_{11} .

Fig. 30. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the power divider. (a) S_{31} and S_{41} . (b) S_{11} and S_{21} .

expectations and the reflection coefficient is maintained at around -20 dB in an 8-GHz bandwidth. The measurements for the 3-dB 90° hybrid in Figs. 30 and 31 and the crossover in Fig. 32 show a small deviation of about 0.5 GHz upward in frequency with respect to the simulation. However, the performance of both devices is acceptable with a band of about 8 GHz with a reflection below -15 dB and an isolation better than 20 dB for the hybrid coupler and better than 30 dB for the crossover at 94 GHz. Due to the frequency shift, the hybrid coupling has an unbalance of 0.4 dB at 94 GHz. The phase difference between its outputs in Fig. 31 is around 90° with a maximum error of 5° in an 8-GHz band. Finally, the crossover transmission parameter represented in Fig. 32(c) has a level of around -0.3 dB at 94 GHz due to copper losses and a

Fig. 31. Phase difference between outputs 3 and 4.

Fig. 32. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the crossover. (a) S_{11} . (b) S_{21} and S_{31} . (c) S_{41} .

Fig. 33. Picture of the manufactured modified Butler matrix.

small resonance at 92.35 GHz. This value coincides with the resonance found in the design of the crossover without pins [see Fig. 17(b)].

B. Final Modified Butler Matrix

This section presents a comparison between simulation and measurement of the final design of the modified Butler matrix and the manufactured prototype, as shown in Fig. 33. The results obtained in simulation and measurement are depicted in Figs. 34–36. The reflection and isolation parameters between the input ports are shown in Fig. 34 with a reflection coefficient below -15 dB in a 6-GHz bandwidth and an isolation better than 20 dB. At 94 GHz, the reflection is below -25 dB at both input ports and the isolation between them is greater than 30 dB. Fig. 35 shows the results of the transmission parameters from the input ports to the output ports. Fig. 35(a) and (b) presents the simulation and measurement of the transmission from port 1 and Fig. 35(c)

Fig. 34. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the modified Butler matrix. (a) S_{11} and S_{22} . (b) S_{21} .

Fig. 35. Simulated and measured S-parameters of the modified Butler matrix. Simulation of transmission from (a) port 1 and (c) port 2 to outputs. Measurement of transmission from (b) port 1 and (d) port 2 to outputs.

and (d) the transmission from port 2. Two resonances appear around the frequencies 92.5 and 95.5 GHz in simulation and measurement. The reasons for the appearance of these resonances are discussed in detail in Section V and solutions are proposed to avoid them. Both resonances are outside the working band, which shows an average output level of -6.8 dB. The additional 0.8 dB is due to losses in copper metallization. The minimum amplitude error appears at 94.17 GHz with values below ± 0.44 dB for port 1 and ± 0.3 dB for port 2.

The full wave simulations of the modified Butler matrix presented in Fig. 36(a) and (c) are practically identical to the results obtained in the design stage of Section III in Fig. 20 by grouping the phase shifts introduced by each component. In the measurements in Fig. 36(b) and (d), phase deviations present a maximum error of 8° for difference configuration and 7° for sum configuration at 94 GHz. However, due to the asymmetry of the path lengths, the phase balance degrades rapidly when separated from 94 GHz with an approximate ratio of $30^\circ/\text{GHz}$. Apart from that, there is a ripple of ± 1 dB in amplitude and $\pm 7^\circ$ in phase which is mainly due to the great difference in lengths between paths. Compared to simulations, this ripple increased due to errors in manufacturing and measurement processes, but only by ± 0.3 dB extra in amplitude and $\pm 1.5^\circ$ extra in phase. Despite this, the prototype fulfills well the desired conditions at the outputs for both input ports

Fig. 36. Simulated and measured phases at the outputs of the modified Butler matrix. Simulation for (a) port 1 and (c) port 2. Measurement for (b) port 1 and (d) port 2. Phase differences are referenced to the phase at port 6.

between 93.75 and 94.4 GHz with a maximum error of 1.5 dB in amplitude and 20° in phase.

Table II shows a comparison with other feeding network designs for monopulse operation or beamforming. The elements included in the comparison are the type of comparator or beamformer used, the number of pieces, parts or layers that compose the networks, the type of transmission line, the manufacturing technology used, the size, characterization of S-parameters and performance of the network in terms of amplitude and phase balance and insertion losses.

The first thing to keep in mind is the difference between designs with magic tee and Butler matrix. The proposals with magic tee present good performance in all aspects, but these structures typically require a multi-level distribution network with several layers. Butler matrices can be designed on a single level, reducing manufacturing complexity, alignment errors and cost. In addition, the proposals with magic tee [16], [40]–[42] are made of metal with expensive manufacturing processes. Only the case in [41] exploits the benefits of 3-D printing with direct metal laser sintering (DMLS) technology in one piece. However, the authors claim that the roughness of the printed surfaces is $25 \mu\text{m}$ using the aluminum alloy AlSi10Mg, whose conductivity is $2.04 \cdot 10^7$ S/m. With these properties of the material, the losses obtained at the frequency of 15 GHz of the design in [41] are of 0.07 dB/cm, but in W-band would rise to around 1 dB/cm. For comparison, losses measured in our prototype are around 0.05 dB/cm at 94 GHz. This high roughness makes the use of DMLS at 94 GHz unfeasible. The proposal in [16] takes advantage of gap waveguide for the distribution network. The design uses multiple layers using CNC milling for the manufacturing process, which is much more expensive than additive manufacturing.

The rest of the proposals in Table II use Butler matrices. The design of most of them is based on SIW manufactured using printed board circuit (PCB) technology. The presence of the dielectric substrate introduces losses greater than 3

TABLE II
COMPARISON WITH PREVIOUS WORKS

Ref.	Feeding network ¹				Physical features		Scattering Parameters ²				Network performance ³		
	Compare/ Beamform	Number of Layers	Type	Manuf.	Size (mm)	Size (λ_0)	f_0 (GHz)	BW (%)	VSWR	Iso. (dB)	AI (dB)	PI (°)	IL (dB)
[40]	MT	19	RW	DB	51x51x4	13.3x13.3x1	78.5	21.9	2	n. a.	0.2	n. a.	n. a.
[41]	MT	1	RW	DMLS	240x240x31	12x12x1.55	15.1	12.9	1.5*	30	0.2*	1.5*	0.15*
[42]	MT	4	RW	SM	40x37.4x2.65	12x11.3x0.8	90.5	15	2	45*	n. a.	n. a.	0.9*
[16]	MT	3	GW	CNC	55x55x8	17.4x17.4x2.5	95	21	2	50	0.5	2	2.2
[14]	BM	1	SIW	PCB	28x30x0.5	8.8x9.4x0.157	94	1.7	2	n. a.	0.2*	5.2*	1.9*
[13]	BM	1	SIW	PCB	130x125x0.5	41x39.4x0.16	94.5	1.6	1.4	n. a.	2.66*	n. a.	7
[43]	BM	2	RW	CNC	58x58x>20	18.2x18.2x>6.3	94	4.3	1.4	21	0.2	n. a.	1
[44]	BM	1	SIW	PCB	93x100x0.5	10.9x11.7x0.06	35	2.9	1.7	25	0.5	n. a.	3
[45]	BM	1	SIW	PCB	140x154x1	8.2x9x0.06	17.53	6	2	25	0.5	5.5	5
[39]	BM	1	SIW	PCB	27x18x0.25	5.4x3.6x0.05	60	6.7	1.5	13.5	2	12	2.5
[46]	BM	5	SISL	PCB	35x34x2.65	3x2.9x0.23	25.5	7.8	1.7	16	1	8	1.1
[47]	BM	1	MS	LTCC	4.2x2.5x1	0.88x0.5x0.2	62.5	1.6	2	n. a.	n. a.	10	7
[48]	BM	1	MS	LCP	58x58x0.05	11.6x11.6x0.01	60	3.3*	2*	17*	1*	10*	2.5*
Our work	BM	1	GW	SLA	160x100x3.9	50.1x31.3x1.2	94	0.7	1.2	23	1.5	20	0.8
							94.17	-	1.12	33	0.44	8.5	

¹ Feeding network: MT: Magic Tee, BM: Butler Matrix. Transmission line: RW: Rectangular Waveguide, GW: Gap Waveguide, SIW: Substrate Integrated Waveguide, SISL: Substrate Integrate Suspended Line, MS: Microstrip. Manufacturing technology: DB: Diffusion Bonding, DMLS: Direct Metal Laser Sintering (3D-Print), SM: Silicon Micromachining, CNCM: Computer Numerical Controlled Milling, PCB: Printed Board Circuit, LTCC: Low Temperature Cofired Ceramics, LCP: Liquid Crystal Polymer, SLA: Stereolithography (3D-Print).

² Scattering Parameters: f_0 : central frequency, BW: relative bandwidth, VSWR: Voltage Standing Wave Ratio, Iso.: Isolation between input ports.

³ Network performance: AI: Amplitude imbalance, PI: Phase imbalance: IL: Insertion loss in the feeding network.

* Simulated value.

dB even in Ku-band [45]. In [43], Butler matrix is based on rectangular waveguide manufactured with CNC milling at 94 GHz. The distribution network is divided into two parts with a cut in E-plane to minimize leakage, but still requires very good alignment and electrical contact between parts. This increases the thickness of the distribution network for connection with WR-10 flanges on the sides and the weight of the parts. The proposal in [46] presents an atypical Ka-band substrate integrate suspended line (SISL)-based design with five stacked layers of dielectric substrate. Losses are relatively low, but not sufficient for W-band. Two proposals use microstrip technology at 60 GHz with manufacturing based on LTCC [47] and liquid crystal polymer (LCP) [48]. Both cases have very high insertion losses and use amplifiers to compensate them.

With respect to bandwidth, the proposed magic tee typically achieves relative bandwidths of 20% with an isolation of more than 30 dB. Butler matrix based designs can reach bands above 2% and isolation above 20 dB. In general, the amplitude unbalance is between 0.2 and 1 dB and the phase unbalance between 2° and 10°. However, many of these results are given only in simulation, since the measured results are from a prototype with the comparator network or beamforming integrated with an antenna.

The prototype presented in this article takes advantage of the high precision of current SLA 3-D printing techniques with copper plating. The result is very smooth surfaces with a metallization roughness around 0.3 μm and a weight of

about 50% with respect to the same piece manufactured in aluminum. This technology applied to gap waveguide allows to drastically reduce the manufacturing costs (a tenth or less than CNC machining), to decrease the complexity of the assembly and to obtain the lowest insertion losses of Table II. Regarding the total size, our proposal seems to be more voluminous than the others. This is due to separating WR-10 flanges sufficiently to enable measurement connection without physical overlap. The dimensions of the final modified Butler matrix integrated with the antenna are smaller ($40.7 \times 18.8 \times 1.2$ normalized to the wavelength). The voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) of 1.2 and isolation better than 23 dB improves the values obtained from some proposals. The amplitude and phase unbalance are better than ± 1.5 dB and $\pm 20^\circ$ respectively in a relative band of 0.7%. These values, worse than those obtained in other proposals, are mainly due to the path asymmetry of the modified Butler matrix. This design consideration was chosen considering that the working band around 94 GHz is very narrow (± 200 MHz, 0.4%) for a monopulse radar, and the values obtained are good enough for the operation of the system. In Table II, we include the values at 94.17 GHz that are comparable to the rest of the proposals. This minimum deviation in frequency allows to validate the viability of the SLA technology for the manufacture of prototypes in W-band.

V. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This section is dedicated to the analysis of the problems encountered in the last stage of prototyping, simulation and

TABLE III
WIDTH MODIFICATIONS

Mode	Wg for $f_c=94$ GHz	Component modified	Previous width	New width
TE ₁₀	1.9 mm	Hybrid 3dB-90°	5.6 mm	4.88 mm
TE ₂₀	3.5 mm	Crossover	5.77 mm	4.68 mm
TE ₃₀	5.1 mm	Sections S4 and S5	3.6 mm	3.15 mm

measurement. All the problems are related to the resonances found in Figs. 32, 34, and 35. These resonances appear because higher order modes are being excited in the structure. In the case of the crossover in Fig. 32, the TE₁₀ and TE₂₀ modes must be excited, but the dimensions allow the TE₃₀ mode to be excited as well. The resonances found in Figs. 34 and 35 for the modified Butler matrix are mainly due to an excess of width in the straight sections S4 and S5 (see Fig. 18) allowing TE₂₀ mode propagation. Table III shows the Wg widths of the basic waveguide gap structure [see Fig. 2(a)] for which modes TE₁₀, TE₂₀ and TE₃₀ begin to propagate at 94 GHz.

As can be seen, the width of the crossover is above 5.1 mm and the width of sections S4 and S5 is above 3.5 mm. Therefore, the resonances found must be eliminated by correcting these dimensions. The authors propose to use the values $n = 2$ and $n = 4$ instead of the current $n = 3$ and $n = 7$ for the hybrid coupler and crossover design. In this way, their dimensions are reduced but they continue allowing a good matching in band. For the phase adjustment in sections S4 and S5, we propose the substitution of the bends of section W (10) by 90° phase shifters to have to correct -47.7° instead of 132.3° . With this change, the width Wg of sections S4 and S5 should be 3.15 mm instead of 3.6 mm for phase adjustment.

VI. CONCLUSION

This article validates the additive manufacturing applied to waveguide gap in W-band. In previous works [33] we already proved the good behavior of this technology at Ka-band, but it is of great interest to test the technology at W-band. The application of additive manufacturing, in particular SLA, on a modified Butler matrix has shown an excellent performance with a high degree of similarity between the simulations and the measurements made. The manufacture and measurement of multiple components corroborate that the results are repeatable. The copper metallization applied on the resin-printed parts offers excellent conductivity and roughness properties, achieving a very low level of losses of approximately 0.05 dB/cm equivalent to a copper surface roughness of 0.3 μm rms. The great versatility of additive manufacturing allows the construction of parts and shapes that are impossible or very expensive to manufacture with traditional technologies such as CNC. This adds degrees of freedom that facilitate the design stage. In addition, the high degree of complexity of the prototypes presented in this article would have meant a great cost of manufacturing time with CNC and the use of tools such as very thin and fragile drills. 3-D-printing has resulted in a significant reduction in the cost of prototyping. The final result is a 3-D-printed modified Butler matrix based on gap waveguide with two inputs and four outputs to generate two different phase configurations: 90° progressive rotation and equiphase. This modified Butler

matrix was proposed for integration into a RLSA monopulse antenna which simultaneously generates a sum and difference diagram with the two phase configurations mentioned in [5]. The measurements made show an amplitude unbalance at the modified Butler matrix outputs of ± 1.5 dB and a maximum phase error of $\pm 20^\circ$. These deviations are acceptable for the correct operation of the monopulse antenna.

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